

the complexes recorded in Nujol mulls with a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer are similar to those of quinoxaline complexes with other metal salts¹⁻⁵, conforming coordination of the two ligand-N atoms to different metal ions, the ligand thus acting as a bidentate bridge (steric positions of nitrogen atoms in quinoxaline precludes chelation). In addition to the absorption bands due to coordinated quinoxaline, the far-IR spectra of the chloro- and bromo-complexes show the halogen dependent terminal^{6,7} Hg-X stretching modes at 320 and 225 cm⁻¹, respectively. The bridging Hg-Br stretching mode in bromo-complex expected at ~150 cm⁻¹ could not be recorded with the present range of the spectrophotometer. However, the molecular weight of the bromo-complex determined by Rast's method (obs. 810, calc. 850) is consistent with the dimeric structure. The molecular weights of the other complexes could not be determined by this method as they were insoluble in camphor.

The IR spectrum of the cyano-complex shows additional absorption bands at 2183, 421 and 325 cm⁻¹ which are identified as $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{HgC})$ and $\delta(\text{HgCN})$ modes respectively, due to coordinated terminal cyano groups⁸. The frequency of $\nu(\text{CN})$ suffers a significant negative shift when the cyano bridges break down and mercury(II) cyanide complexes with terminal cyano groups absorb at lower frequencies than pure mercury(II) cyanide containing bridging cyano groups⁸. Furthermore, $\nu(\text{HgC})$ shift to higher frequencies in complexes containing bridging cyano groups and this positive shift may be attributed to coupling of $\nu(\text{HgC})$ with $\nu(\text{CN})$ in the HgCN part of the molecule. Since terminal cyano groups absorb at lower frequencies than pure $\text{Hg}(\text{CN})_2$, the terminal $\nu(\text{HgC})$ and $\delta(\text{HgCN})$ modes would also be expected to absorb at lower energies as are observed here for terminally bonded cyano groups⁸. The thiocyanato-complex shows absorption bands at 2117, 717 and 439 cm⁻¹ which are assigned as $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{CS})$ and $\delta(\text{SCN})$, respectively, of the coordinated thiocyanato groups. The frequencies of these modes are consistent with those normally associated with terminal S-bonded thiocyanato groups^{9,10}.

From spectral results it is suggested that chloro-, cyano- and thiocyanato-complexes have polymeric four-coordinated tetrahedral geometry around the metal atoms with two terminally bonded anionic groups and the two nitrogens of the bidentate bridging quinoxaline molecules. The bromo-complex has been assigned a dimeric four-coordinated structure involving both bridging as well as terminal bromide ions.

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Optimal Temperature (T_{opt}) for Maximal Thermal Conductivity (K_{max}) of Solids at Low Temperatures**

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IN continuation of our earlier communication¹, we now discuss the success of the said equation by calculating the T_{opt} value for many solids to the second order of approximation (S.O.A.) and examine the improvement achieved thereby over the value obtained for the same to the first order of approximation (F.O.A.) in respect of the latest reported^{2,3,4} observed values.

The three-term-thermal conductivity equation, which has been successfully utilized for obtaining a meaningful and informative reduced low-temperature thermal conductivity expression⁵ for solids of widely varying nature, embracing metals, semi-conductors, insulators including molecular crystals and chemical compounds, has been expressed¹ as

$$K = \frac{T}{\alpha + \delta T^2 + \gamma T^3} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{1}{K} = \frac{\alpha}{T} + \delta T + \gamma T^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

from which the expression for T_{opt} is obtained¹ as

$$T_{\text{opt}} = (\alpha/4\gamma)^{1/3} \{ [1 + \sqrt{1 - \delta^3/27\alpha\gamma^2} - \delta^3/54\alpha\gamma^2]^{1/3} + [1 - \sqrt{1 - \delta^3/27\alpha\gamma^2} - \delta^3/54\alpha\gamma^2]^{1/3} - \delta/6\gamma \} \quad \dots (2)$$

where, according to the most recent views⁶, α , δ and γ are constants being respectively related to the scattering of phonons by geometrical factors including impurities, the effect of anharmonic coupling

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TABLE 1

Solids	Calculated values for $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ (recorded up to the second place of decimal)	Difference between the T_{opt} values for the two approximations (recorded up to the third place of decimal)	Calcd. values for $T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ (recorded up to the second place of decimal)	Observed value ^{2,3,4} for T_{opt}	% deviation of $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ value from the observed value ^{2,3,4} (recorded up to the first place of decimal)	% deviation of $T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ value from the observed value ^{2,3,4} (recorded up to the first place of decimal)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Silicon	22.14	2.100	24.24	25	11.44	3.0
Tin	1.97	0.045	2.01	2	1.5	0.5
Iron	14.20	0.061	14.26	15	5.3	4.9
Niobium	11.44	0.400	11.84	13	12.0	8.9
Palladium	8.54	0.018	8.56	9	5.1	4.8
Platinum	7.96	0.030	7.99	8	0.5	0.1
Osmium	15.63	0.050	15.68	20	21.9	21.6
Rhodium	16.41	0.413	16.82	18	8.8	6.5
Ruthenium	19.65	0.200	19.85	20	1.7	0.8
Thorium	7.56	0.044	7.60	8	5.5	5.0
Tungsten	8.76	0.145	8.91	10	12.4	10.9
Zinc	4.70	0.020	4.72	6	21.6	21.3
Neon	3.14	0.074	3.21	3.5	10.2	8.3
Quartz	7.75	0.027	7.78	9	14	13.5
Synthetic Sapphire	54.25	5.582	59.83	56	3.1	6.8

of phonons⁷ and phonon-phonon interaction. T_{opt} to the first order and second order of approximations are obtained as

$$T_{opt(F.O.A.)} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} - \delta/6\gamma \quad \dots (3)$$

and

$$T_{opt(S.O.A.)} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} \{1 + (2^{2/3} \cdot \delta^2) / (36\alpha^{2/3} \cdot \gamma^{4/3})\} - \delta/6\gamma \quad \dots (4)$$

from which we obtain

$$T_{opt(S.O.A.)} - T_{opt(F.O.A.)} = (\alpha/2\gamma)^{1/3} \{ (2^{2/3} \cdot \delta^2) / (36\alpha^{2/3} \cdot \gamma^{4/3}) \} \quad \dots (5)$$

$T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ value for fifteen solids of various nature has been calculated by utilizing equation (5), in combination with our results for $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ reported earlier¹. The values are recorded in Table I which also enlists the values for $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ and the differences between the said two approximations. The percentage disagreement from the observed^{2,3,4} values of the two approximations has also been recorded in the table for easy and ready reference.

Considering the reported^{2,3,4} uncertainties in the observed values of the solids, discussed in this paper, the results obtained appear to contribute fairly towards the success of the three-term-empirical equation published elsewhere¹. As expected, the $T_{opt(S.O.A.)}$ value, in general, shows an improvement over the $T_{opt(F.O.A.)}$ value, being closer to the observed value, in all cases. The synthetic sapphire is, however, an exception. This may, perhaps, be due to the probability of greater inaccuracy in the determination of its thermal conductivity in the low-temperature region.

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The Kinetics of Oxidation of D (+) Glucose by Potassium bromate in Acid Medium

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THE kinetics of the oxidation of D(+)-glucose has been extensively studied using different oxidising agents, e.g., Ce(IV)¹, Cu(II)² in alkaline medium, ammoniated AgNO₃³, Pb(OAc)₄⁴, K₃Fe(CN)₆ in